

Figure S3. Protein–protein interaction network and MCODEs of merged proteins upregulated 2 h after OFC in the OFC-positive and OFC-negative group

Densely connected protein–protein networks were identified using the Molecular Complex Detection (MCODE) algorithm in Metascape. Blue circles: proteins in Serum-UpPOS2. Red circles: proteins in Serum-UpNEG2. The biological interpretation of each MCODE is presented in Table S1.